
De-Psychologizing Benevolence. Lotze's Ethics between Kant, Herbart, and the British Moralists

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Abstract: In this article I examine R. H. Lotze's attempt to ground morality in benevolence without thereby appealing to the constitution of human nature. In the first section I consider Francis Hutcheson's earlier approach, who understands benevolence as a fundamental affection characterizing human psychology. The second section briefly turns to Kant's critique of Hutcheson. The third section discusses some basic concerns of Lotze's ethics. Subsequently, I reconstruct Lotze's analysis in chapter two of the *Grundzüge der praktischen Philosophie*, where he puts forward the claim about the foundational role of benevolence for ethics. I conclude with some considerations about the promise and problems of Lotze's approach.

Keywords: Lotze, Kant, Herbart, benevolence, British moralists

There is some consensus among interpreters that Lotze's practical philosophy is underdeveloped and saddled with tensions that cannot be easily resolved within the framework of his thought. To give but one example, Frederick Beiser writes that besides the problem of incompleteness "[t]here are more troubling questions of consistency, which are indeed so vexing that it is questionable whether Lotze has a coherent ethics at all" (Beiser 2013, 290). In particular, Beiser denounces the co-existence of empiricist and rationalist motifs in Lotze's writings on ethics, such as the preeminent significance of pleasure (Lotze 1885a: 692; Lotze 1885b: 17) and the staunch defense of innate moral ideas having unconditional validity (Lotze 1891: 522); however, although it is certainly true that Lotze did not live to develop a fully rounded and systematic ethical theory, what we find in his writings is not merely a hodgepodge of incoherent motifs, but rather the attempt to transform and recast creatively elements of ethical theory inherited from traditions as different as Kantian transcendental thinking and, most importantly, eighteenth century British moral philosophy.

In this regard, it is puzzling that despite all emphasis on Lotze's quest for an absolutely binding moral principle that would provide ethics with a solid foundation, Beiser is silent just about what Lotze thinks such principle is. While correctly recognizing that "this little book provides the best conspectus of Lotze's ethics" (Beiser 2012: 289) Beiser skips altogether chapter two of the *Grundzüge der praktischen Philosophie* (Beiser 2012:292-293), which Lotze concludes with the following strong and unambiguous statement: "the idea of benevolence must give us the sole supreme principle of all moral conduct" (Lotze

1885b, 34). Hence, in order to assess fairly the status of Lotze's ethics, it is imperative to understand just what he means by this statement and how he believes it can be philosophically justified. 'Benevolence' is famously one of the key notions in eighteenth century British moral philosophy, featuring prominently in the writings of Francis Hutcheson, Joseph Butler, and David Hume. Lotze is thus reviving an old idea roughly one century years after its original formulation, but, as we will see, in a completely different philosophical context and with a different goal in mind.

In this paper I want to argue that Lotze's reflections on ethics in the *Grundzüge* is best characterized as an attempt to de-psychologize benevolence, that is, to develop a notion of benevolence that does not revolve around specific claims about human nature and is not identified with a specific feeling. This does not mean that Lotze sees no connection between ethical demands and human nature, or that he fails to recognize that in humans benevolence does often manifest itself as a definite feeling; however, Lotze is careful to distinguish principles of morality that are directly related to human nature and principles that can be presented as binding ideals, regardless of how our nature happens to be constituted and how they happen to manifest themselves therein. His approach is then to try and disentangle benevolence from a number of other principles of moral agency that depend on human nature and show that is foundational vis-à-vis all the other benevolence principles that are required of an action in order for it to count as moral. In so doing, Lotze is trying to strike a balance between Kant's formalism, which he considers insufficient for reasons to be explained in what follows, and Herbart's pluralism of the moral principles, which refuses to place one single formal principle at the foundation of ethics. Lotze thinks that a properly understood notion of benevolence does just this kind of philosophical job, and thus hopes to surpass both Kant and Herbart in laying the foundations of ethics.

The paper has five sections: in the first section I summarize briefly the views on benevolence found in the work of Hutcheson. In the second section I touch upon Kant's critique of benevolence, in order to then turn to Lotze in the third section. After presenting some of the basic concerns in Lotze's ethical writings in section three, I examine closely chapter two of the *Grundzüge*, where he puts forward the claim about the fundamental significance of benevolence in ethics. I conclude with a brief assessment of the promise and problems of Lotze's approach.

1. Benevolence in Hutcheson

Philosophical arguments about the nature, scope, and relevance of our concern with the happiness of others date back at least to Aristotle's *Nicomachean Ethics*, where a mutual well-wishing attitude is described as a fundamental ingredient of true friendship. In the writings of eighteenth century British moralists, benevolence assumes a much more encompassing function and is repeatedly described as the psychological phenomenon in which morality originates. As T.A. Robertson argues with reference to Francis Hutcheson: "All moral motives can be subsumed under benevolence, that is, an affection that seeks as its object the good of another" (Robertson 1973: 7). Hutcheson describes benevolence in these terms in various passages of his early work *An Inquiry into the Original of our Ideas of Beauty and Virtue*, originally published in 1725, particularly in the second treatise *An Inquiry Concerning Moral Good and Evil* (e.g. Hutcheson 2004: 104). By calling benevolence an affection, or at times a desire (Hutcheson 2004: 103), Hutcheson wants to convey a few important points. First, benevolence is not a product of reasoning. This implies that accounts of benevolence that reduce it to the outcome of calculation based on self-interest misconstrue its psychological nature. This leads to the second important point: as an affection or desire benevolence is not the sort of psychological state that can be summoned at will. As Hutcheson puts it: "Neither Benevolence, nor any other Affection or Desire can be directly raised by Volition" (Hutcheson 2004: 220).¹ By contrast, benevolence is declared to be a fundamental aspect of human nature, i.e., an affection that arises naturally under the appropriate circumstances and whose occurrence anyone can witness upon correct introspection. Third, in keeping with the empiricist tenets of his approach, by declaring benevolence an affection Hutcheson wants to stress its function as *motivation* for action. This is important for the kind of intuitionist account of the objectivity of morality championed by Hutcheson. On this account, we all possess a moral sense that enables us to apprehend certain actions as motivated by benevolence and, hence, as moral. Not only do we apprehend such actions as moral but when we reflectively become aware of our emotional response to them, we experience a sense of approval and support for what we are seeing. This generates the desire to not hamper the work of benevolence within us and let this natural affection determine our behavior as thoroughly as possible and toward the largest possible circle of people (Hutcheson 2004: 91). Indeed, as Hutcheson's influential precursor Joseph Butler argued, acting benevolently toward others is doubly rewarding.² First, we experience the kind of gratification that follows the satisfaction of any natural desire, such as hunger or thirst. The natural desire to contribute to the good of others procures such gratification when we actually manage to do so. In addition, by acting benevolently we also experience a second-order kind of gratification, that is, the self-approval that follows our reflective awareness of the work of benevolence within us (see Roberts 1973: 59-60).

In sum, for Hutcheson, "the quality of an action that makes it moral is its benevolent motivation. Once we consult our approvals and disapprovals we know that it

could not be otherwise, that nothing more can be added" (Loughran 1986: 297). Confidence in the reliability of our approvals and disapprovals is ultimately rooted in Hutcheson's theological convictions. It is God who provided us with a moral sense, hence its deliverances are binding, unless other unruly passions interfere. If we set aside all references to theology, as Hume would eventually have it, then we must conclude that there is something absolutely contingent about how our psychology works, and that the fact that a passion like benevolence inclines us to seek the good of others is nothing but a brute fact about human nature as we know it. As Richard Price eventually argued, we could imagine a possible world in which those feelings that we currently associate with benevolence attach to self-love instead, or even to very different kinds of psychological states. Moreover, we could wonder whether it really is the good of others that gratifies us when we act benevolently or perhaps that second-order self-approval that Butler and Hutcheson describe is not really the first (and perhaps the only) psychological mechanism that drives our eagerness to tend to the happiness of others. If this were the case, then the true motivation behind benevolent acts would be the morally questionable desire to feel pleased about ourselves.

2. Kant's critique of benevolence

This last point about the potentially ambiguous motives involved in the psychology of benevolence is in fact one of Kant's main critiques to Hutcheson's attempt to ground morality in a feeling (the affection of benevolence) and its reflective endorsement through the moral sense. In a seminal paper Dieter Henrich (2009) has already explored in great detail Kant's indebtedness to and critique of the Scottish thinker. Therefore, it will suffice here to recall in a few brushstrokes the main points of Kant's criticism, in order to then highlight the problem subsequently inherited, so to speak, by Lotze. Kant's fundamental issue with Hutcheson's approach is that grounding morality in a feeling is incompatible with the universality and necessity required by moral principles. This is, in fact, the fundamental premise of Kant's analysis: "that a law, if it is to hold morally, that is, as a ground of an obligation, must carry with it absolute necessity" (Kant 1997: 2 [4: 389]). Feelings, by contrast, "merely possess a private validity" (Henrich 2009: 34) and they are "by nature variable in their degree of intensity" (Henrich 2009: 34). Furthermore, due to their intrinsic particularity and variability, "feelings are not forms of knowing" (Henrich 2009: 35). If feelings were responsible for disclosing the fundamental principle of morality, we would not be in a position to tell whether such principles are binding on all humans. By contrast, for Kant moral experience must be guided by a rational principle, that is, by a principle whose application draws on capacities that are thoroughly rational, rather than emotional. Third, if our confidence in the deliverances of the moral sense is exclusively contingent upon a theological conviction about its origin in God, then it's unclear whether morality is good for its own sake or just a factual arrangement of things that God may have willed otherwise. Finally, as hinted above, Kant perceptively notices that the feelings evoked by benevolence might be

actually self-directed, that is, to put it simply, feeling the impulse to tend to the happiness of others might be truly motivated by a desire to feel good about ourselves. The double reward English moralists associated with benevolence might turn out to be a threat, rather than an advantage to the project of grounding morality in human psychology; hence, Kant's well-known plea for a "a pure moral philosophy, completely cleansed of everything that may be only empirical and that belongs to anthropology" (Kant 1997: 2 [4: 389]).

Before moving to consider Lotze's proposal in the next section, it is important to notice a couple of important points that follow from Kant's rejection of benevolence as the principle of morality. First, let us note the shift occurring in Kant in the very idea of finding the *principle* of morality. For Kant asking about the principle of morality no longer means asking about the factual motivation of moral actions, i.e., the psychological spring behind them. Rather, for Kant finding the principle means identifying some element that makes actions moral independently of how creatures having our contingent psychological makeup actually act. Kant's well-known appeal to evaluating the maxim of our action under the perspective of universality embodies just this shift. The maxim of an action is arguably nothing but the action as such regardless of the psychological 'milieu', in which it happens to occur. As Alfredo Ferrarin puts this point in his recent book on Kant, moral agency is entirely contingent upon reason's ability to represent the moral law to itself; in so doing, "by affecting itself, reason [...] motivates itself to action" (Ferrarin 2015, 128). Thus, for Kant reason does not have to seek a motivation to act morally outside itself. Rather, by representing to itself the moral law and thus recognizing the categorical imperative as the form of moral agency, reasons induces itself to act correspondingly, thus determining itself autonomously. As we shall see, Lotze retains this Kantian notion of principle. Seeking the *Grundsatz* of morality does not mean seeking the psychological motivation of moral behavior, but seeking the 'fundamental ingredient', so to speak, of moral agency.

While this reformulation of the notion of principle certainly has its philosophical 'benefits', it is important to also realize its philosophical 'costs'. Kant's shift entails a thoroughgoing form of rationalism. The will is declared to have a rational structure. It is, indeed, a kind of rationality that cannot be reduced to mathematical reckoning or the subsumption of appearances under concepts. Nonetheless, moral behavior is declared to be a matter of rational deliberation, i.e., construing the maxim of an action and considering how the world would turn out to be if that maxim became a universal law. Several philosophers after Kant found this dominance of universalizing rationality over the domain of ethics problematic, since they perceived it as a failure to preserve the autonomy of ethics (see for instance Rickert 1914: 207) and a lack of sensitivity to the inevitable contingency and individuality of ethically relevant situations.

Hence, the following question arises: Would it be possible to "fix" benevolence in such a way as to preserve its substantial, other-directed trait but elevate it to the dignity of principle in Kant's sense, free of all references to the vagaries of human psychology? If it were possible to purify

benevolence from its merely empirical connotation and the fluctuation that characterizes human feelings, then we would have a principle in Kant's sense, but one that (1) is distinctively ethical, rather than generically rational, (2) retains a connection with important features of human psychology, while not being reducible to them, and (3) cannot be charged of formalism, as Kant's appeal to universality has been. This is precisely what Lotze has in view.

3. The basics of Lotze's ethics

As mentioned in the introduction, Lotze's reflections on ethics can be found in three short texts. The first is Book V, Chapter V in the first tome of Lotze's *opus magnum* *Microcosmus: An essay concerning man and his relation to the world* (1885a). The chapter is titled "Conscience and morality" (Lotze 1885a, 682-714). The second is a transcription of lectures held in Berlin under the title *Grundzüge der praktischen Philosophie* (Lotze 1885b). The third is a short article published posthumously by one of Lotze's students under the title *Nachgelassener Aufsatz über die Principien der Ethik* and later reprinted in the third volume of Lotze's *Kleine Schriften* (Lotze 1891).

While each text emphasizes or prioritizes different elements in the philosophical investigation of morality, all three have as a common denominator the refusal to disconnect ethical principles from the tendency toward pleasure. Lotze opposes a kind of eudaemonism that identifies pleasure with the *principle* of ethics (Lotze 1885b, 12-13), but he nonetheless thinks that in a universe populated by "beings of bare intelligence" (Lotze 1885b, 17), i.e., entities who distinguish truth and falsehood but feel neither pleasure, nor pain, "it would be quite incomprehensible that there should be definite rules which should obligate spiritual beings to any one definite form of conduct, and forbid them another form" (Lotze 1885b, 17-18).³ In other words, pleasure (and pain) are not to be regarded as justificatory principles to choose certain actions over other. Rather, pleasure and pain are fundamental *facts*, whose existence generates the problem of finding principles of conduct in the first place. It should be noticed that Lotze's point about the necessary relation between pleasure and pain and the very project of ethics is most emphatically not meant to be a claim about human nature. Lotze is adamant at the very beginning of his inquiry that looking for the principles of ethics through an analysis of human nature is a non-starter (Lotze 1885b, 8-9). Not only is it difficult to adjudicate the validity of claims about human nature in light of historical and cultural variability. Even if we possessed a perfectly clear and thorough body of knowledge about our nature, it would still remain to be discussed whether we *ought* to follow our nature or rather work against it. Lotze's point about the connection of pleasure and morality is rather a conceptual point about the inseparability of two notions and the 'fact of pleasure and pain' as the basis of the very problem of good and evil.

This way of presenting things very much resembles Lotze's take on the status of one fundamental law of cognition, namely, the principle of sufficient reason. In *Logic* (1888) Lotze writes: "It is not impossible to conceive

a world in which everything should be as incommensurable with every other thing as sweet is with triangular, and in which therefore there was no possibility of so holding two different things together as to give ground for a third: it is true that, if such a world existed, the mind would not know what to do with it, but it would be obliged to recognize it as possible according to its own judgment” (Lotze 1888, 95). Similarly, the mind would not know what to do with ethical principles in a possible world entirely deprived of pleasure and pain. Lotze’s claim is actually even stronger with regard to the fact of pleasure and pain. He thinks that we would not be able to recognize the connections holding among things if mastering those connections were not directly relevant to the increment of pleasure and the reduction of pain: “For the fact that besides all which exists and which happens according to settled laws, there is also enjoyment of both, also pain and pleasure, this fact cannot, it seems to us, be regarded as a mere addendum to the order of the world, all necessary connection of things would be to us incomprehensible if we could not regard it as simply the foundation upon which to build up a world of joy and sorrow” (Lotze 1885a, 683).

Lotze interprets Kant’s failure to recognize the *a priori* connection between pleasure and morality as an overreaction due to the desire to radically decouple the idea of morality and the idea of self-interest. But while we certainly cannot construe moral demands merely as imperatives generated by what an individual empirical subject deems pleasurable at a certain time, the very idea of moral value and morally valuable actions makes no sense if it is disconnected from all relation to pleasure. Lotze clarifies his point with an appeal to ideal agency: “That would be of supreme value which caused satisfaction to an ideal mind in its normal condition, a mind which had been purified from all tendency to diverge from its proper path of development. Beyond this summit there is no foothold, and the idea of an object possessing value, which is altogether unconditioned, which does not show its value by its capacity to produce pleasure, shoots beyond the mark” (Lotze 1885a, 690).

Kant himself needs an implicit reference to pleasure and pain, happiness and misery in order for his procedure for the assessment of actions under the standpoint of universality to make sense: “Why, in fact, do we consider it as a matter of course that the maxims of our action must fit into a general system of law? And which are the maxims which do not thus fit in? Plainly those which, if generally followed, would produce general disorder and the frustration of all effort. But what is this acknowledgment of the importance of order, and of the possibility of carrying out our intention, if it is not either (a) a grand and comprehensive utilitarian principle taking the place of special and narrower ones, or (b) the confession that maxims different from those demanded would lead to general misery, and are therefore to be rejected?” (Lotze 1885a, 690). Lotze’s point is well-taken, particularly with regard to Kant’s construal of imperfect duties (Kant 1997, 32-33 [4:423]), such as the duty to help others in need. Kant’s reasoning to argue for the impossibility to will indifference to others in need as a universal law clearly refers to the unpleasant experience of needing help and being ignored: “For a will that decided this would conflict with itself, since many cases could occur in which one

would need the love and sympathy of others and in which, by such a law of nature arisen from his own will, he would rob himself of all hope of the assistance he wishes for himself” (Kant 1997, 33 [4:423]). It is admittedly hard to see how a duty like helping others in need would even be thinkable if all references to pleasure and pain dropped out of the picture.

Lotze is much more attracted to Herbart’s aesthetic approach to ethical agency, which stands in open contrast to Kant’s. According to Herbart, “the ethical axioms, [...], must not only be immediately obvious and certain, but must also have a definite content” (Lotze 1885b, 15). In short, such content is discovered through an analysis of elementary relations among wills, which conscience has to judge and declare agreeable or disagreeable. Lotze, too, believes that conscience must be the ultimate tribunal for discernment in ethical matters: “There must be a voice of conscience which gives direction in particular cases concerning the praiseworthiness or blameworthiness of an action presented before it” (Lotze 1885b, 10). In Herbart’s view, the voice of conscience leads to the identification of a “plurality of ethical primary judgments” (Lotze 1885b, 15) pertaining to intuitively pleasing relations among wills. Herbart mentions five such relations: “inner freedom; perfection; benevolence; right; fairness/justice” (Kim 2015; see also Beiser 2014, 125-130). Unlike Herbart, however, Lotze believes that it should be the task of a scientific discipline like philosophy to try and produce systematic unity among the relations conscience intuitively identifies by tracing back all moral principles to one that underlies all the other (Lotze 1885b, 15-16). This is what he undertakes in chapter two of the *Grundzüge*, to which we shall now turn.

4. Benevolence as the fundamental ethical principle

Chapter two of the *Grundzüge* opens with the thesis that there are actions demanding our “unconditional approbation” (Lotze 1885b, 23). Finding out what these are procures pleasure of a distinctively intellectual kind. The way to do so is by analyzing the concept of action [*Handlung*], which Lotze sharply distinguishes from other forms of causal efficacy [*Wirken*] originating in us, such as involuntary bodily movements. For Lotze, in order for a movement to count as an action it has to fulfill four conditions: (1) its point of departure has to be a “conscious idea of what is to be attained” (Lotze 1885b, 24); (2) it must have been chosen among other, consciously considered courses of action; (3) it must be accompanied by consciousness of the respective value of the possible courses of action; (4) it must start with an explicit decision (Lotze 1885b, 24). Note that this conception of action is deliberately narrow. It excludes, for example, the exercise of skillful habituated movements and all forms of so-called ‘mindless coping’ in the world. It implies that while humans can be certainly characterized as rational agents, they do not *act* all the time, but only occasionally.

Given this definition of action, Lotze proceeds to analyze the transcendently necessary conditions for something like an action to be possible in the first place. Such conditions are regarded as principles of action in the Kantian sense explained above. They are originally constituti-

ve of actions, but when they become aware through philosophical reflection they henceforth count as foundations for agency and can be self-consciously pursued. Lotze identifies *four* groups of principles.

The first group of principles pertains to the “excitability of the soul” [*Erregbarkeit des Gemüts*] and the “warmth of feeling” (Lotze 1885b, 25; translation modified) that are required in order for a movement to count as an action, rather than a mechanical happening of nature. In other words, there has to be some level of participation in the happiness or unhappiness brought about by one’s activity. The excitability of the soul carries with it (1) some level of intensity; (2) some level of differentiation [*Vielseitigkeit*], i.e., it cannot be one-sidedly stimulated by just one class of objects; (3) an appropriate proportion that correlates with the actual value of the object in question. A subject acting either with absolute indifference, or touched exclusively by a single class of objects, or else disproportionately moved by the objects of her choice would not be considered as performing actions by Lotze’s standards.

The second group of principles pertains to how an action should be carried out. Lotze mentions “resignation”, “energy”, and “conscientiousness” (Lotze 1885b, 27). By resignation Lotze means the awareness of the things we can change and those we can’t, as well as the realism to not waste time on these latter. Energy signifies resoluteness, i.e., once embarking upon an action, an agent should carry it out resolutely and to the end. Conscientiousness is the requirement to act out of what, *ceteris paribus* and to the best of our knowledge, strikes us as our duty.

The third and most important group of principles is germane to the *content* of action, i.e., the way in which the action brings about or prevents changes in the world. The first principle is worth a full quote because, as Lotze will argue a few lines down, it is the fundamental principle of all morality: “The piety is everywhere well-pleasing, that considerably allows every natural product and every natural event [...] to be undisturbed and to develop itself; and that even sustains (so far as this is possible) the development of such product or event, but never interferes to disturb it without being justified in doing this by some special reason. This principle condemns every aimless impulse at destruction even of what is inanimate. Such piety naturally attains its larger moral value in the relation of subjects to subjects, and in this case forms what we call Benevolence” (Lotze 1885b, 29; translation modified). We shall return to this characterization of benevolence shortly. Let us first enumerate the other principles of this group and those of the fourth and last, in order to then evaluate Lotze’s systematic move. The second content-related principle is self-limitation, i.e., the readiness to give others who happen to be interested in the same thing as ourselves their fair share, whenever this is possible. Third, Lotze mentions retribution [*Vergeltung*], i.e., “the returning of a corresponding measure of reward or of punishment to a will which has occasioned a definite measure of weal or woe” (Lotze 1885b, 30).

The fourth and last group pertains to the personality of the agent, understood as the enduring psychological makeup of the subject of action. Since actions flow from persons having a certain psychological stability, the fol-

lowing three principles must be counted among the transcendental conditions of agency: consistency, moral habit, specific individual character (Lotze 1885b, 30).

In the closing section of the chapter Lotze sets out to determine what principle should be regarded as fundamental, that is, what kinds of action ‘please unconditionally’. This move is consistent with his foregoing critique of Herbart, who failed to provide a systematically grounded theory of moral agency and limited himself to listing a variety of actions that are declared to be intrinsically pleasing. As for the first group, Lotze argues that it entails a series of “gifts of nature, over which we rejoice if they exist, and the total lack of which would annul completely every ethical judgment: but the intensity of which cannot be manufactured at will by the living spirit, but can only hover before it as a goal to be attained” (Lotze 1885b, 32). In other words, the excitability of the soul, its intensity, multi-sidedness, and proportion are rooted in our human nature and they cannot be meaningfully construed as ethical *demands* proper. I cannot demand of another that their soul be more reactive to morally relevant situations, or more intensively so, or that their reactivity expand to include a larger range of situations. These things may or may not happen, they may be the object of hope or ideal striving but they ultimately just pertain to the way in which humans are factually constituted.

As for the second and fourth group, Lotze argues that they are merely *formal* principles of agency that could very well encompass immoral behavior, if they were not accompanied by the awareness of the pleasure and pain caused by the action under scrutiny. After all, nothing prevents an agent from consistently, energetically, conscientiously, etc. pursuing some evil. We can also have very specific individual characters and ‘moral’ habits (in the original, ethically neutral sense of *mores*) that are invariably oriented toward evil deeds.

It is the third group that encompasses the principles directly pertaining to ethical agency. Lotze writes: “It is only the third group which comprises those moral ideas that of themselves excite unconditioned approbation. But even among the three members of this group, this is really accurate only of *Benevolence*.” (Lotze 1885b, 33) It is, in fact, only due to the association of strife with pain that we place value on self-limitation, or it is only by reference to unfair distributions of pleasure and pain that we consider retribution and the ensuing ideal of justice as ethically compelling. Lotze closes this section all-too briefly with the following statement: “We therefore return to the quite simple and fundamental thought previously propounded. There is such a thing as moral judgment of conduct only upon the assumption that this conduct leads to pleasure or pain. But to this conscience joins the further truth, that it is not the effort after our own, but only that for the production of another’s happiness, which is ethically meritorious; and, accordingly, that the idea of benevolence must give us the sole supreme principle of all moral conduct” (Lotze 1885b, 33-34). In other words, while the unconditional approbation directed toward self-limitation and retribution can be traced back to awareness of pains and pleasures caused or endured, the very fact of caring for the well-being of others cannot be further traced back to some more original, ethically relevant relation.

These sections are admittedly far too sketchy to provide a full and convincing philosophical justification of the claims Lotze puts forward therein; however, the philosophical move Lotze is attempting is clear enough. First, note that there is no reference whatsoever to human psychology with regard to benevolence. The principles that are directly related to human psychology are confined to the first group mentioned above. This should take care of Kant's concern that benevolence would be subject to varying degrees of intensity in different people and would therefore be unreliable as a principle of morality. On Lotze's account, intensity and the emotional responses associated with benevolence can be distinguished from benevolence itself. They are attributes of the kind of soul that experiences benevolence rather than intrinsic properties of benevolence as such. Moreover, on Lotze's account benevolence is not an affection that functions as the spring for moral actions. Our actions can have multifarious psychological origins. Whatever their actual psychological origins may be, a group of actions distinguishes itself as eliciting a kind of unconditional approbation that is impervious to reduction to some other principle. It is telling that Lotze describes benevolence as a specific kind of piety vis-à-vis fellow subjects. Piety is not primarily a psychological impulse to act, but rather a disposition not to disturb something's natural development, and, in the case of benevolence, to let others flourish according to their specific nature. This means that under certain circumstances acting benevolently could amount to not acting at all. Being concerned with the happiness of the other is thus not a psychological primary affection that drives our behavior, as it is the case in Hutcheson, but rather the fundamental ingredient of a distinctive class of other-directed actions that are immediately pleasing, and hence elicit unconditional approbation. To use the language of Lotze's later *Ethik-Aufsatz* (Lotze 1891, 530), this certainly has a psychological corollary that can be described in terms of feeling and emotions. But for Lotze 'benevolence' does not name primarily a feeling or an emotion but the other-directed quality of an action (or a refusal to act) that wills the flourishing of another according to the spontaneous development of her nature. Benevolence has thus been effectively de-psychologized.

But isn't this move extremely counterintuitive? Isn't it perfectly clear that whatever else we might want to mean by 'benevolence' at a minimum it has to be some kind of feeling, or mental state, or disposition that we can introspectively identify within ourselves? Does it make any sense to counterpose benevolence as a Kantian principle and benevolence as a psychological experience?

To conclude this section it is helpful to clarify once again how Lotze thinks we are able to discover fundamental principles that are *per se* independent from the facticity of our experience, human nature, etc. but nonetheless reveal themselves therein. Some passages of the later *Ethik-Aufsatz* are quite explicit about this matter. Here, Lotze defends the innateness of fundamental epistemological and moral principles, a point which might be read as proving that he cannot do without some claims about human psychology, and even about metaphysics. Lotze, however, explains that by 'innate', he means "having unconditionally binding sanctity" (Lotze 1891, 530) and not that the principles of ethics are factually there *as such*

(i.e., *qua* principles) from the outset in our mind. He argues that the "content and validity of moral ideas is independent from the experience that occasions their development in consciousness" (Lotze 1891, 531). Knowing that the moral idea *par excellence* is benevolence, we shall infer that the content and validity of benevolence (i.e., not disturbing and possibly fostering the flourishing of others) is independent from experiences that occasion its development in individual consciousness. How are we to picture, then, the relationship between benevolence *as a principle in the Kantian sense* and benevolence as a set of feelings, dispositions, etc. occurring in the consciousness of human individuals?

Lotze writes: "Only after having repeatedly acted according to such principles is it possible for subsequent reflection to cast a comparative retrospective look at these multifarious actions and discover in them the rule, according to which one has hitherto acted. Only at this point is it possible to make that, which earlier was only the mind's necessary mode of action a conscious principle that the mind henceforth follows as such" (Lotze 1891, 523).

This quote perfectly renders Lotze's de-psychologizing strategy for benevolence. His point is not that benevolence should not be counted among the emotional experiences of humans or considered a distinctive trait of their nature. Rather, Lotze wants to say that we can lift up benevolence to the level of a principle in the Kantian sense regardless of its origin in human psyche. The reason why benevolence should be considered the fundamental principle of ethics is not that it invariably occurs as an affection in the human mind, but that it is the fundamental ingredient in order for an action to be approvingly perceived as moral. What goes on in the human mind instantiating that action is only, as hinted above, a "psychological corollary" (Lotze 1891, 530) and not the ground of benevolence's validity as an ethical principle.

5. Conclusion

Let us briefly summarize the results of this investigation. Lotze repositions at the center of moral philosophy benevolence, a notion that used to be prominent among eighteenth century British moral philosophers such as Francis Hutcheson, but was subsequently jettisoned by Kant. Like Herbart before him, Lotze believes that Kant's ethical theory is vitiated by an excessive rationalism that prevents him from duly recognizing the role of pleasure and pain (and, correlatively, of emotionally-driven approval and disapproval) for the very problem of morality. He also believes that the voice of conscience has the power to intuitively recognize certain forms of behavior (i.e., in Herbart's terms, relations among wills) as ethical and that the task of practical philosophy is to identify those forms and trace them back systematically to one fundamental principle, which he identifies with benevolence. Unlike his eighteenth century predecessors, however, Lotze does not identify benevolence with an affection or an emotional state of mind originating in human nature. On Lotze's account benevolence can be considered as a principle of moral action *as such*. It is described as the tendency to not disturb and possibly foster the flourishing of others according to the spontaneous development of their nature.

Exhibiting benevolence in this sense is the *conditio sine qua non* for action to be recognized as moral, regardless of the psychological makeup of the entity in which the action in question is instantiated and the feelings that accompany it.

One of the advantages of Lotze's treatment of morality as founded in benevolence is that it places the relation to others at the very heart of ethics. Unlike Kant, who considers morality a matter of the will's relation to itself, hence, of self-relation, Lotze's ethics is entirely grounded in an other-directed principle; however, in the same way in which Kantians typically need quite a bit of philosophical work to explain why self-related moral obligations necessarily entail other-related moral obligations (it is questionable whether any Kantian has provided an entirely satisfactory theory on this matter), a Lotzean might have a hard time explaining how benevolence toward others entails obligations toward oneself. It seems that describing an ethical relation to oneself in terms of 'not disturbing' or 'possibly fostering' one's spontaneous development is at best odd.

Furthermore, while the de-psychologization of benevolence certainly elevates it to a more-than-empirical principle, it completely removes its function of being a natural motivation to act morally, which was actually its main appeal among eighteenth century British philosophers. Lotze thus owes us a theory of moral motivation, which he never produced. While we can be ready to recognize the 'unconditionally binding sanctity' of moral principles, it is not obvious that we are ready to accept them as *our* principles. Lotze's theory is good to reassure a person who already recognizes the work of benevolence within her that the content and validity of benevolence is not just a matter of human psychology, that might as well be otherwise, but a fundamental trait of moral behavior as such. It is not, however, equipped to respond to the moral skeptic or simply to the philosopher raising what Christine Korsgaard effectively calls "the normative question" (Korsgaard 1996, 10) i.e., the question about the origin of morality's authority over us.

While Lotze's theory is certainly less than satisfactory on these important issues, this paper was meant to show that it is by no means inconsistent or contradictory, as recent commentator Frederick Beiser suggests. It should be considered a serious and original, yet incomplete attempt to reconcile the demands of emotionalism and rationalism, thereby striking a middle-ground between Kant, Herbart, and the British moralists.

Notes

¹ In light of this explicit remark, it is rather puzzling to read in the introduction to the most recent edition of the *Inquiry* that for Hutcheson "benevolence is not an emotion or a feeling, but an act of the will" (Leidhold 2004: xv). We can definitely hope or wish to be (more) benevolent, and such hope or wish can be expressed by acts of the will, but for Hutcheson benevolence is most definitely *not* an act of the will.

² It should be noted that the status of benevolence in Butler as an affection or as a superior principle more akin to conscience and rationality is disputed. Discussion of this point would exceed the scope of this paper. For an informative discussion see McNaughton 1992.

³ Incidentally, Lotze's position on this matter coincides with the one defended some fifty years later by Husserl: "The practical behavior of human beings is manifestly determined by feeling. Were we to extinguish all feeling from the human breast, all our ethical concepts, con-

cepts such as means and ends, good and bad, virtue and duty and all the ancillary concepts would lose their meaning." (Husserl 2004, 147-148)

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